

Informed Consent

You are being invited to participate in a research study titled Assessing the Sustainability Awareness of University Students. This study is being done by [REDACTED] from [REDACTED]. You were selected to participate in this study because you are a student at [REDACTED].

The purpose of this research study is to examine students' sustainable behavior and their knowledge about environmental sustainability. If you agree to take part in this study, you will be asked to complete an online survey. This survey will ask about the sustainability behaviors you engage in and your knowledge about sustainability. It will take you approximately 10 minutes to complete.

During this research study, no risks or discomforts are anticipated. The survey does not include any identifying information and the data from the survey will be kept in a password-protected file and deleted after the research is completed. Your participation in this research study, your responses, or any individual results will be maintained by the PI and all members of the research team.

Your participation in this survey, and all responses you give, are anonymous. The survey includes no identifying information. The data collected for this study will be stored until the end of 2024. Results of this study, not any individual responses, may be shared through academic presentations, peer-reviewed publications, and conference presentation.

You do not have to agree to participate in this research study. If you do choose to participate, you may choose not to at any time once the study begins by simply closing out of the survey. There is no penalty for not participating or withdrawing from the study at any time. If you are a CCU student, your decision to participate or not will have no effect on your grade.

If you have any questions about this research study, please feel free to [REDACTED]. The Institutional Review Board (IRB) under the Office of Sponsored Programs and Research Services is responsible for the oversight of all human subject research conducted at Coastal Carolina University. If you have any questions about your rights as a research participant before, during, or after the research study, you may contact this office by calling [REDACTED].

This research study has been approved by the IRB on November 29, 2023. This approval will expire on November 28, 2024, unless the IRB renews the approval before this date.

Do you consent to participate in this study?

- A. Yes (please complete the survey below)
- B. No (please do not complete the survey below)

Please answer six questions about yourself.

1. What is your classification at [REDACTED]?

- A. Freshman
- B. Sophomore
- C. Junior
- D. Senior
- E. Graduate
- F. Non-degree Seeking
- G. Other/Not Sure

2. Under what college is your primary major at [REDACTED]?

- A. Business
- B. Education & Social Sciences
- C. Health & Human Performance
- D. Honor College
- E. Humanities & Fine Arts
- F. Science
- G. Undeclared
- H. Not sure

3. What is your gender?

- A. Female
- B. Male
- C. Other
- D. Prefer not to specify

4. Which political party do you support?

- A. Democratic
- B. Republican
- C. Green
- D. Another Party
- E. I am an independent voter
- F. Not sure or do not care about politics

5. What is your current cumulative GPA at [REDACTED]?

- A. Between 3.50 and 4.00
- B. Between 3.00 and 3.49
- C. Between 2.50 and 2.99
- D. Between 2.00 and 2.49
- E. Below 2.00
- F. I do not know or prefer not to say
- G. I do not have a cumulative GPA since it is my first semester at CCU

6. How many courses did you take in college or elsewhere that included at least one module on sustainability or sustainable environmental practices?

- A. 0 courses
- B. 1 course
- C. 2 courses
- D. 3 or more courses

For the next 10 questions, please indicate using the following scale – 0 (never), 1 (rarely), 2 (occasionally), 3 (about half of the time), 4 (most times), and 5 (always) – how often you engage in each of these:

7. Use a reusable bottle to avoid buying single-use plastic bottles.

(Never) 0 1 2 3 4 5 (Always)

8. Use reusable bags instead of plastic bags when shopping.

(Never) 0 1 2 3 4 5 (Always)

9. Recycle plastics, papers, and metals.

(Never) 0 1 2 3 4 5 (Always)

10. Compost organic trash such as fruits, vegetables, and coffee beans.

(Never) 0 1 2 3 4 5 (Always)

11. Donate or sell unwanted items instead of throwing them away.

(Never) 0 1 2 3 4 5 (Always)

12. Purchase used items instead of new products.

(Never) 0 1 2 3 4 5 (Always)

13. Carpool, cycle, or use public transportation to save on gasoline.

(Never) 0 1 2 3 4 5 (Always)

14. Turn off the lights when I leave a room.

(Never) 0 1 2 3 4 5 (Always)

15. Take short showers to save water.

(Never) 0 1 2 3 4 5 (Always)

16. Buy organic fruits and vegetables.

(Never) 0 1 2 3 4 5 (Always)

Please answer the following questions to assess your knowledge of environmental sustainability. Please do not use any help or outside information when completing these questions. Remember, your answers are anonymous.

17. What is the term for the process of breaking down used materials into raw materials to make new products?

- A) Reusing
- B) Remission
- C) Recycling*
- D) Reducing

18. Which of these energy sources is considered renewable?

- A) Nuclear power
- B) Wind energy*
- C) Coal
- D) Natural gas

19. Which of the following items is typically NOT recyclable in most curbside recycling programs in the United States?

- A) Glass bottles and jars
- B) Aluminum cans
- C) Plastic shopping bags*
- D) Cardboard boxes

20. What is the largest source of greenhouse gas emissions in the United States?

- A) Transportation*
- B) Agriculture
- C) Industrial processes
- D) Residential buildings

21. What is the best sustainable alternative to single-use plastic bags for grocery shopping?

- A) Paper bags
- B) Biodegradable plastic bags
- C) Reusable cloth bags*
- D) Styrofoam bags

22. What is a common practice in the United States to reduce water usage and promote sustainable agriculture?

- A) Irrigating crops with untreated wastewater
- B) Implementing water-efficient irrigation systems*
- C) Trapping rainwater in large containers
- D) Dumping excess water into rivers and lakes

23. What type of light bulbs are the most energy-efficient and longest lasting and, thus, best for the environment?

- A) Halogen bulbs
- B) Fluorescent bulbs
- C) LED bulbs*
- D) Candle bulbs

24. What is the term for the U.S. federal program that provides incentives for the installation of solar energy systems on residential and commercial properties?

- A) Sustainable Energy Initiative
- B) Solar Power Grant Program
- C) Green Energy Rebate Scheme
- D) Investment Tax Credit (ITC)*

25. Which household activity typically consumes the most water in the US?

- A) Washing dishes
- B) Flushing the toilet*
- C) Taking a shower
- D) Watering the garden

26. Which type of plastic is commonly used in single-use water bottles and is known to have environmental impacts?

- A) PET (Polyethylene Terephthalate)*
- B) PVC (Polyvinyl Chloride)
- C) HDPE (High-Density Polyethylene)
- D) LDPE (Low-Density Polyethylene)